

DEVELOPMENT OF CARBON FIBRE

REINFORCED TITANIUM-COPPER COMPOSITES

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Summary

The development of carbon fibre reinforced titanium-rich copper alloys (up to 35 wt. % Cu) is described, with particular emphasis on the fibre-matrix chemical reaction. Assessment of the effects of matrix composition, processing temperature and time on the longitudinal tensile properties of the composites is made.

Introduction

In the last few years there has been an increasing commercial interest in the development of practical composite materials made up of light metals (e.g. aluminium, magnesium and titanium) acting as the matrix, reinforced with strong refractories such as alumina, silicon carbide based and boron carbide based fibres or whiskers (1,2). The success of such composites depends on satisfactory bonding between the metal matrix and the non-metallic component to achieve the highest stress transfer from the matrix.

Carbon fibre and titanium metal are possible attractive constituents for the manufacture of strong and light composite material. Carbon fibre has high modulus, high strength, high thermal stability and low density, and titanium possesses high specific strength at elevated temperatures and extremely good corrosion resistance. However, molten pure titanium is a highly reactive liquid and therefore during the fabrication process an extensive fibre-matrix chemical reaction takes place which may give rise to fibre degradation and poor composite properties. In order to obtain effective bonding between the metal matrix and the reinforcing constituent, some wetting is essential. This may be achieved without the occurrence of strong chemical interaction which may cause degradation, and partial or even complete dissolution of the non-metallic. It is known that molten titanium wets and reacts with carbon fibre to form stable titanium carbide. However, it may be possible to influence its wetting characteristics and retard its chemical interaction by alloying it with metals which are chemically inert towards carbon, for example, copper which does not wet carbon below 1560K. The alloying addition helps lower the processing temperature and consequently may reduce the severity of fibre degradation without adversely affecting the bonding of the fibre with the alloy matrix.

In this work, the development of carbon fibre reinforced titanium-rich copper alloys containing -25 wt.% and -35 wt.% Cu is attempted. Particular emphasis is laid upon the influence of matrix composition on the fibre-matrix reaction zone at various processing temperatures and times. The effect of fibre volume fraction upon the unidirectional tensile properties of the metal matrix composites is also investigated.

Experimental Techniques

Commercially pure titanium (99.9%) and electrolytically refined copper (99.98%) were used in this investigation to produce titanium-rich copper alloy matrices reinforced with carbon fibres of round cross section (10 μ m diameter). The as-received yarn, which contained 500 fibres, was carefully cut to 150 mm lengths and co-axially sandwiched between clean titanium wires, 2 mm in diameter and of the same length. The two constituents of the composite were then wrapped with clean copper ribbon (3 mm wide and 1 mm thick), producing a bundle of ~ 25 mm diameter. The arrangement of the composite constituents prior to fabrication is schematically shown in Fig. 1.

The chosen alloy matrices of composition Ti-35 wt.% Cu and Ti-25 wt.% Cu exhibited liquidus temperatures of 1370K and 1550K respectively. These temperatures are well below the melting point of pure titanium (1948K). The estimated percentages by volume of carbon fibres incorporated into the composites were in the range of 8 - 35%.

The titanium-copper matrix was formed by R.F. heating of the composite bundles in a water-cooled silver boat under a dynamic high purity argon atmosphere. The fabrication temperature was maintained close to the liquidus

Figure 1 - Arrangement of the MMC constituents prior to fabrication.

Tensile specimens were machined from the composite rods and tested at room temperature on a 10KN servo hydraulic Instron. The 0.2% proof stress ($\sigma_{0.2}$), ultimate tensile stress (σ_{UTS}) and percentage elongation were determined for typically three specimens of each matrix composition and fibre content.

Results and Discussion

The transverse micrographs of Ti-25 wt.% Cu with approximately 30% and 10% by volume of the carbon fibres are shown in Figs. 2 and 3 respectively. The micrographs demonstrate that the fibres are separated and dispersed fairly uniformly, and clearly showing the success of the technique used in incorporating effectively the fibres into the alloy matrix.

Figure 2 - Optical micrograph of Ti-25% Cu containing ~ 30 vol.% carbon fibre

Figure 3 - Scanning electron micrograph of Ti-25% Cu containing ~ 10 vol.% carbon fibre

Fig. 3 reveals extensive reaction zones surrounding the fibres in a specimen which was fabricated at 1555K for a period of ~ 720 s, and Fig. 4 shows the quantitative X-ray analysis data obtained for the fibre-matrix reaction zone of the same specimen. The analysis obtained for a number of interaction zones point to the rejection of solute element, Cu, ahead of

advancing titanium carbide phase, TiC, during freezing. Therefore, the chemical reaction which takes place between titanium and carbon at the fabrication temperature results only in the formation of a stable titanium carbide phase at the interface.

Figure 4 - Typical X-ray analysis trace shown for the Ti-25% Cu alloy containing ~ 10 vol.% fibres

Figure 5 - Plots of interaction zone thickness vs. \sqrt{t}

The thickness of the reaction zone was determined as a function of fabrication time for the two matrices. The values of the reaction zone thickness are plotted versus \sqrt{t} for Ti-25% Cu and Ti-35% Cu, containing ~ 10 vol.% carbon fibres, as shown in Fig. 5. As the results indicate, the growth of the reaction product, TiC, is diffusion controlled. It should therefore be possible to control diffusion at the fibre-matrix interface during the fabrication process to obtain an optimum level of the interfacial phase. The previous studies on other reactive composite systems have shown that interfacial reaction need not interfere with the property improvements if the extent of reaction is controlled and if the reaction does not weaken and degrade the reinforcing constituent (3). In the present study, the metallographic observations of the longitudinal sections of the composite rods revealed some evidence of discontinuous interfacial reaction product, particularly in those samples which were subject to relatively long holding time (> 360 secs.) at the fabrication temperature, see Fig. 6. But all other cases, the fibre-matrix boundaries exhibited continuous layers of the reaction product. It is found that the tensile performance of the composites is greatly affected by the morphology of the titanium carbide phase.

Figure 6 - Optical micrograph of longitudinal section of Ti-25% Cu containing ~ 30 vol.% fibres

The influence of the fibre addition is best assessed by the tensile testing results, as the longitudinal tensile properties of unidirectional metal matrix composites depend not only upon the intrinsic strength of the reinforcing constituent but also upon the stress transfer capability of the interaction zone (4). Table I presents the mean values for $\sigma_{O.2}$, σ_{UTS} and percentage elongation for the composites which were held for ~ 240 s. at the fabrication temperature. It should be pointed out that the composites which

were held beyond ~ 240s. at the fabrication temperatures showed a distinct deterioration in their tensile properties.

Table I. Tensile Properties

Composition wt. %	Vol. % Fibre	$\sigma_{0.2\%}$ MPa	σ_{UTS} MPa	Elong. %
Ti-25 Cu	0	131	197	2.7
	10	177	305	1.6
	20	146	243	< 1
	30	151	184	< 1
Ti-35 Cu	0	161	241	1.9
	10	206	469	1.3
	20	198	392	< 1
	30	142	169	< 1

The results clearly indicate that the specimens did not demonstrate true composite behaviour. However, there was some improvements in 0.2% proof stress and ultimate tensile strength particularly in those specimens which were fabricated at 1370K for short lengths of time < 240 secs. and contained 10 - 20% by volume of fibres. Those composites which were fabricated at higher temperature (1550K), for longer periods of time (> 240 s) and possessed high % by volume of fibres invariably revealed extensive and discontinuous reaction zones, which adversely affected their tensile properties. It is suggested that the deterioration of tensile properties is associated with the irregular morphology of the interaction product, which could probably act as stress concentrators, giving rise to poor tensile strength of the fibres and consequently the composite as a whole.

Conclusions

An approach was successfully devised in incorporating carbon fibres into low melting points titanium-rich copper matrices. The generation of titanium carbide phase at the fibre-matrix interface is time and temperature dependent. The tensile properties of the composite is sensitive to the morphology of the formed interfacial phase.

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